

TO LOVE OR NOT TO LOVE

To love is the flame, that dares the night,
Whisper carried on, as in an infinite light.
Building temple in the heart's deep core,
Opening the doors we never knew before.
Not to love, is it a silent tragedy, a shield?
A barren field where no song is revealed.
It guards the soul from fracture and pain,
Yet it leaves the dark sky without its rain.
But since to love is risky, as fall and flight,
Paradox as woven as in shadow and bright.
Not to love, seems as safety, but is a stone,
Every echo unfortunately so returns alone.
As the question lingers, as soft yet severe:
Is wound, worth for wonder we hold dear?
To love or not! as hardest choice we weave,
But who can trust to love and really believe?

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Inspired from W.Shakespeare's

“ TO BE OR NOT TO BE ”

